

Navigating Senior Fellowship through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

Alex Claudiu Avadanei

Alex Claudiu Avadanei, Chartered Psychologist and Senior Fellow, reflecting on his own progression, recognises how three pillars of SDT have shaped his career and reinforced his decision to pursue Senior Fellowship.

After completing my MSc in Organisational Psychology, my journey in higher education began as an hourly paid lecturer while working towards my Postgraduate Certificate in Education (PGCE). Now, eight years later and having held several educational leadership positions, my passion for elevating teaching quality, mentoring colleagues, and driving institutional change has led me to manage postgraduate MSc programmes, a transition that has been both challenging and deeply rewarding.

At the core of this evolution lies **Self-Determination Theory (SDT)** (Deci & Ryan, 2012; 2024), which posits that individuals are most motivated and fulfilled when three psychological needs are met:

- **Autonomy** – the ability to make independent decisions and shape one's environment.
- **Competence** – the confidence and capability to succeed in one's field.
- **Relatedness** – a sense of connection and impact within a community.

Senior Fellowship (SFHEA) aligns perfectly with SDT, as it requires educators to demonstrate autonomy in their leadership, competence in shaping institutional practice, and relatedness in mentoring others. Reflecting on my own progression, I see how these three pillars have shaped my career and reinforced my decision to pursue Senior Fellowship.

Why I chose to apply for Senior Fellowship

The transition from **Fellow (FHEA)** to **Senior Fellow (SFHEA)** is not just about personal development; it is about **influencing and shaping the academic experiences of others**. One key difference is that Senior Fellowship requires evidence of how one's practice has not only evolved but also impacted students, colleagues, and institutional culture.

Applying for **Senior Fellowship** was a natural step for me because it allowed me to reflect on how I had already been fulfilling the three core needs of Self-Determination Theory:

- **Autonomy** – Leading academic initiatives, standardisation workshops, and pedagogical innovations
- **Competence** – Developing expertise in inclusive teaching, assessment design, and reflective practice
- **Relatedness** – Mentoring colleagues, supporting students, and fostering a culture of collaboration.

Through this process, I came to understand that my role was no longer just about my own teaching practice, it was about empowering others and driving meaningful change in higher education.

Making a difference: strengthening 'Autonomy, Competence, and Relatedness'

One of the most rewarding aspects of my journey has been fostering **a sense of autonomy and competence in others**. Through standardisation workshops, which I lead alongside colleagues, we aim to enhance assessment consistency and fairness, ensuring clarity and alignment across postgraduate modules. This initiative has not only improved students' learning experiences but also empowered educators with greater control over their teaching and assessment methods, enhancing their professional autonomy

Mentoring colleagues has been another significant aspect of my leadership. Many educators face **imposter syndrome** or uncertainty about their teaching approaches. By encouraging reflective practice and guiding them through curriculum development, assessment strategies, and student engagement techniques, I have helped them build competence and confidence in their academic roles.

Culturally responsive teaching and the power of relatedness

A fundamental aspect of Self-Determination Theory is relatedness, the need for meaningful social connections. In higher education, this translates into fostering an inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment.

Beyond students, relatedness also applies to academic colleagues. My efforts in mentoring, collaborating on pedagogical projects, and leading faculty development sessions have strengthened relationships within the institution. Through shared goals and mutual support, we have built a community that prioritises continuous professional development and student success.

Lessons learned: The power of self-determination in higher education

Reflecting on my Senior Fellowship journey, I recognise that the key to meaningful academic leadership lies in balancing autonomy, competence, and relatedness. This journey has **reinforced the importance of self-reflection, continuous learning, and fostering growth in others.**

By applying the Self-Determination Theory, I have not only enhanced my own motivation and professional satisfaction but also contributed to an environment where educators and students feel empowered, competent, and connected.

Self-Determination Theory & Senior Fellowship

What's next? A call to action

For those considering **Senior Fellowship**, I encourage you to reflect on your own experiences:

- **How have you fostered autonomy, competence, and relatedness in your career?**
- **What leadership initiatives have you led that have shaped the experiences of students and colleagues?**
- **How can you leverage reflective practice to drive further change?**

I invite you to share your thoughts and engage in this vital conversation about how leadership in higher education can be guided by self-determination and inclusive teaching practices.

Alex Claudiu Avadanei is a Chartered Psychologist and academic leader dedicated to enhancing teaching and learning practices in higher education. In 2025, he achieved his Senior Fellowship, marking a significant milestone in a career defined by a commitment to excellence, continuous growth, and impactful leadership.

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About

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